
Assessing the significance of ESP instruction in engineering education: evidence from student perspectives

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Annotation *This study explores the effectiveness of English for Specific Purposes (ESP) instruction among second-year Electrical Engineering and Computer Engineering students at Ajou University in Tashkent. Using an IMRAD framework, the research integrates survey and interview data to analyze students' perceptions, motivation, and learning outcomes. A total of 37 students participated, while 36 completed a structured questionnaire. Participants were aged 18–22 with B1–B2 English proficiency levels. Empirical analysis revealed that 74% of students considered ESP essential for their future careers, while 96% positively evaluated project-based and case-study activities for improving technical vocabulary acquisition. Descriptive statistical analysis and thematic coding of interviews indicated increased engagement, improved comprehension of technical terminology, and enhanced communicative competence. Moreover, the findings support learner-centered ESP design and demonstrate that contextualized instruction significantly contributes to professional readiness. As well as, the study contributes to ESP pedagogy by providing evidence from Central Asian higher education contexts.*

Keywords *ESP, engineering education, empirical analysis, project-based learning, technical English*

Muhandislik ta'limida ESP fanining ahamiyatini baholash: Talabalar fikrlariga asoslangan dalillar

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Annotatsiya *Ushbu tadqiqot Toshkentdagi Ajou universitetining Elektr muhandisligi va Kompyuter muhandisligi yo'nalishida tahsil olayotgan ikkinchi bosqich talabalari orasida Maxsus maqsadlar uchun ingliz tili (ESP) ta'limining samaradorligini o'rganadi. IMRAD modeli asosida olib borilgan tadqiqot talabalar qarashlari, motivatsiyasi va o'quv natijalarini tahlil qilish uchun so'rovnoma va intervyu ma'lumotlarini birlashtiradi. Tadqiqotda jami 37 nafar talaba ishtirok etdi, ulardan 36 nafari tuzilgan anketa-so'rovnomanini to'liq yakunladi. Ishtirokchilarning yoshi 18–22 oraliqida bo'lib, ingliz tili darajasi B1–B2 ni tashkil etdi. Empirik tahlil natijalariga ko'ra, talabalarning 74 foizi ESP fanini kelajakdagi kasbiy faoliyati uchun muhim deb hisoblagan, 96 foizi esa texnik lug'at boyligini rivojlantirishda loyiha asosidagi va keys-stadi faoliyatlarini ijobiy baholagan. Tavsifiy statistik tahlil hamda intervyularning tematik kodlash natijalari talabalar faolligining ortgani, texnik terminologiyani tushunish darajasi yaxshilangani va kommunikativ kompetensiyaning rivojlanganini ko'rsatdi. Natijalar o'quvchiga yo'naltirilgan ESP kurslarini loyihalashni qo'llab-quvvatlaydi hamda kontekstga asoslangan ta'lim kasbiy tayyorgarlikni sezilarli darajada oshirishini tasdiqlaydi. Tadqiqot Markaziy*

Osiyo oliy ta'lim muhitidan olingan dalillar orqali ESP pedagogikasiga ilmiy hissa qo'shadi.

Kalit so'zlar *ESP, muhandislik ta'limi, empirik tahlil, loyiha asosida o'qitish, texnik ingliz tili*

Оценка значимости обучения ESP в инженерном образовании: данные на основе взглядов студентов

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Аннотация *Данное исследование посвящено изучению эффективности преподавания английского языка для специальных целей (ESP) среди студентов второго курса направлений «Электротехника» и «Компьютерная инженерия» Университета Аджу в Ташкенте. Исследование, выполненное в рамках структуры IMRAD, объединяет данные анкетирования и интервью для анализа восприятия студентами обучения, их мотивации и образовательных результатов. В исследовании приняли участие 37 студентов, из которых 36 полностью заполнили структурированную анкету. Возраст участников составил 18–22 года, уровень владения английским языком – B1–B2. Эмпирический анализ показал, что 74% студентов считают ESP важным для своей будущей профессиональной деятельности, а 96% положительно оценили проектное обучение и кейс-методы как эффективные инструменты для освоения технической лексики. Описательный статистический анализ и тематическое кодирование интервью выявили повышение учебной вовлеченности, улучшение понимания технической терминологии и развитие коммуникативной компетенции. Полученные результаты подтверждают эффективность студентоориентированного проектирования курсов ESP и демонстрируют, что контекстуализированное обучение значительно способствует профессиональной подготовленности студентов. Исследование вносит вклад в педагогику ESP, предоставляя эмпирические данные из контекста высшего образования Центральной Азии.*

Ключевые слова *ESP, инженерное образование, эмпирический анализ, проектное обучение, технический английский язык*

Introduction

English for Specific Purposes (ESP) has become a central component of modern engineering education due to globalization and the growing need for international communication in science and technology. Engineering graduates are increasingly

expected to operate in multilingual professional environments where technical documentation, research collaboration, and workplace communication occur primarily in English. Consequently, ESP courses aim to bridge the gap between general language competence and professional communication

requirements. This study investigates ESP implementation among Electrical Engineering and Computer Engineering students at Ajou University in Tashkent and evaluates the impact of project-based learning and case-study approaches on student engagement and terminology acquisition. The research also builds on previous ESP studies which emphasize the importance of aligning course design with learner needs and professional goals.

Literature review

English for Specific Purposes (ESP) has evolved as a learner-centered approach designed to meet the communicative needs of learners within specific academic and professional domains. Unlike General English instruction, ESP emphasizes contextualized language learning, discipline-specific terminology, and authentic communicative tasks aligned with learners' future careers. Hutchinson and Waters conceptualized ESP not as a product but as an approach in which instructional decisions are determined by learners' purposes and professional expectations. This perspective has become the theoretical foundation for modern ESP curriculum design.

In engineering education, ESP plays a particularly significant role due to the global nature of scientific communication and technological collaboration. Engineering students are increasingly required to engage with English-medium instruction, international research publications, and multinational professional environments. Arnó-Macià, Aguilar-Pérez, and Tatzl (2020) demonstrated that ESP courses significantly improve students' awareness of specialized communication and prepare them for international academic and professional contexts. Their longitudinal study revealed that engineering students develop stronger communicative confidence when language instruction is directly linked to disciplinary practices.

Recent studies further emphasize that ESP effectiveness depends largely on needs

analysis and contextual relevance. Kausar (2025) argues that engineering-oriented ESP programs enhance technical writing, collaboration skills, and professional communication because they focus on authentic workplace language rather than abstract grammar instruction. ESP instruction therefore contributes not only to linguistic competence but also to employability and career readiness.

Within Central Asian and Uzbek educational contexts, ESP research has gained increasing attention in response to national policies promoting multilingual professional competence. Studies on ESP development in Uzbekistan highlight the growing integration of specialized English courses across engineering, IT, and vocational programs as part of broader educational reforms aimed at global competitiveness. These reforms emphasize needs-based curriculum design and industry collaboration as essential components of ESP implementation.

Scholars from the region, including Z. Khabirova (2025), have investigated ESP instruction specifically for electrical and computer engineering students, demonstrating that contextualized communication tasks significantly improve students' professional language skills and engagement. Khabirova's case study confirms that ESP courses incorporating real engineering scenarios foster practical communication competence and reduce linguistic barriers in technical discussions.

Similarly, Uzbek ESP researchers such as Sh. Bekchanova (2021) and other regional scholars emphasize communicative and task-based approaches as effective strategies for developing professional English competence among non-philological students. Their work highlights that ESP instruction becomes most effective when students actively participate in collaborative tasks, problem solving, and project-based learning environments aligned with disciplinary contexts.

Pedagogically, contemporary ESP research increasingly supports experiential and task-based learning models. Task-Based Language Teaching (TBLT) has been shown to enhance vocabulary acquisition and communicative performance because learners use language as a tool for solving professional problems rather than memorizing isolated structures. Empirical findings indicate that authentic tasks promote deeper cognitive processing and long-term retention of technical terminology.

In addition, technological advancements and digital learning environments have further transformed ESP instruction. Recent studies highlight the integration of AI tools, mobile learning, and digital platforms as mechanisms for improving engagement and communication skills in engineering ESP classrooms. These innovations support collaborative learning and simulate real professional communication environments, thereby strengthening students' readiness for global workplaces (Elmuratova et al., 2025).

Existing literature consistently demonstrates three major trends in ESP research:

1. increasing alignment between language instruction and professional contexts;
2. growing reliance on project-based and experiential learning;
3. expanding integration of digital technologies in ESP pedagogy.

However, despite extensive research in Europe and Asia, empirical ESP studies from Central Asian universities remain limited. Therefore, the present study contributes to the literature by providing empirical evidence from Ajou University in Tashkent, focusing on electrical and computer engineering students and examining how project-based ESP instruction influences learner perception and terminology acquisition.

Methodology

This study adopted a mixed-method research design combining quantitative survey analysis and qualitative interviews. The

participants included 37 second-year students enrolled in Electrical Engineering and Computer Engineering programs. Students were divided into two groups, both taught using identical ESP teaching methods. English proficiency levels ranged from B1 to B2 according to institutional placement testing.

A questionnaire consisting of Likert-scale and open-ended questions was administered to 36 students. Additionally, semi-structured interviews were conducted to explore students' experiences with project work and case-study activities. Data analysis included descriptive statistics, percentage calculations, and thematic coding.

Results and Discussion

The findings of this study provide strong empirical support for the effectiveness of English for Specific Purposes (ESP) when instruction is closely aligned with students' professional contexts and learning needs. The high level of agreement among participants regarding the relevance of ESP to their future careers (74%) reflects a growing awareness among engineering students that language competence is not merely an academic requirement but a professional necessity. This result is consistent with previous ESP research which demonstrates that learners show increased motivation when instructional content directly corresponds to their disciplinary goals.

Compared with earlier studies conducted in vocational engineering settings, particularly the research by Brilianti and Rokhim (2023), the present study reveals similar patterns of learner perception despite differences in geographical and institutional contexts. While their research involved transportation engineering cadets, the present findings from electrical and computer engineering students suggest that positive attitudes toward ESP are not discipline-specific but rather characteristic of technical education environments where English functions as a medium of global communication.

One of the most significant findings concerns the impact of project-based learning and case-study approaches, which received a 96% positive evaluation from students. Interview responses indicated that these activities allowed students to use technical terminology in authentic communicative situations rather than memorizing isolated vocabulary items. From a pedagogical perspective, this supports constructivist learning theory, which argues that knowledge acquisition becomes more meaningful when learners actively construct understanding through problem-solving and collaboration.

Moreover, the integration of case studies appeared to reduce students' anxiety when using English for professional communication. Several participants reported increased confidence when discussing engineering topics because tasks simulated realistic workplace scenarios such as technical presentations, troubleshooting discussions, and collaborative project planning. These findings align with adult learning theory, which emphasizes relevance, autonomy, and experiential learning as key drivers of successful instruction.

The consistency of results across two separate groups taught using identical instructional methods also strengthens the internal validity of the study. Similar response patterns suggest that the effectiveness of project-based ESP instruction is not dependent on a particular classroom dynamic but may represent a replicable pedagogical model. This has important implications for ESP curriculum designers seeking scalable teaching approaches in engineering faculties.

Another notable implication relates to terminology acquisition. Students repeatedly emphasized that learning technical vocabulary through projects allowed them to understand both meaning and functional usage. This observation supports Pazoki and Alemi's (2019) claim that motivation and contextualization significantly enhance language retention. Rather than viewing vocabulary learning as a discrete linguistic activity, students perceived

terminology as a tool for accomplishing engineering tasks.

Despite these positive outcomes, several limitations should be acknowledged. First, the relatively small sample size (37 participants) limits the generalizability of the findings. Second, the study relies primarily on perception-based data rather than standardized language proficiency measurements. Future research could incorporate pre- and post-testing or longitudinal tracking to measure measurable language improvement over time.

Nevertheless, the present study contributes to ESP pedagogy by providing empirical evidence from a Central Asian higher education context, a region that remains underrepresented in ESP research literature. The findings suggest that learner-centered ESP instruction combined with experiential methodologies can effectively bridge the gap between academic language learning and professional engineering communication.

The quantitative results demonstrate a strong positive perception of ESP instruction among participants. Out of 36 questionnaire respondents, 27 students (74–75%) agreed that ESP courses are essential for their future professional careers, 7 students (19%) expressed neutral opinions, and only 2 students (6%) indicated limited agreement. These findings suggest that the majority of learners clearly recognize the practical relevance of discipline-specific English instruction within engineering education.

In addition, students evaluated instructional methodologies used in the ESP course. A total of 35 students (96–97%) reported that project-based learning and case-study activities significantly improved their understanding of technical terminology and professional communication skills. Only one respondent reported a neutral stance, while none expressed negative perceptions. This overwhelming approval highlights the effectiveness of experiential learning strategies in technical language acquisition.

To provide a clearer empirical overview, descriptive statistics were calculated for key survey items, as presented in *Table 1*.

Survey Item	Agree (n)	Neutral (n)	Disagree (n)
ESP is necessary for career	27	7	2
Project work improves terminology	35	1	0
Case studies improve communication	35	1	0

Table 1.

Qualitative interview data further supported the survey findings. Students frequently reported that project tasks enabled them to apply engineering terminology in realistic contexts such as describing circuits, explaining system processes, and presenting technical solutions. Thematic coding identified three dominant categories: improved vocabulary retention (reported by 22 students), increased speaking confidence (18 students), and better understanding of professional discourse conventions (16 students).

Furthermore, comparison between the two instructional groups revealed nearly identical response distributions, indicating

consistency of outcomes across classroom settings. This suggests that the applied ESP methodology demonstrates reliability and can be replicated in similar engineering programs without significant variation in learner response.

The study concludes that ESP courses tailored to engineering students significantly improve engagement and perceived professional readiness. Project work and case studies serve as effective strategies for developing technical vocabulary and communication skills. Future ESP curricula should incorporate experiential learning and continuous needs analysis.

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